

2. Steps in using the IFDC dispenser method. IFDC. 1986. a) Workers use device for line transplanting. b) Worker transfers USG. c) Workers pick up USG. d) Workers deep-place USG by hand.

control transplanting geometry and plant populations.

The IFDC dispenser method enables small-scale rice farmers to efficiently use 30-60 kg N/ha as USG to significantly increase rice yields. It can serve as an intermediate technology for medium-scale farmers until suitable machines are developed for the effective deep placement of USG. It may not be labor efficient for large-scale rice farmers. □

Testing a seed drill for upland rice

P. C. Senapati, P. K. Mahapatra, and D. Satpathy, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, India

We tested six seed drills (Table 1) for upland rice during 1983-86 wet seasons

in a randomized block design with three replications.

Soil was lateritic, coarse-textured, well drained, strongly acidic, and low in nutrients. Rice variety Subhadra (90 d duration) was dry seeded at 75 kg seeds/ha with 60-18-33 kg NPK/ha. All P and K and 25% N were applied at sowing; 50% N was topdressed 20 d

Table 1. Features of seed drills. Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, 1983-86.

Drill	Drill features						
	Width (cm)	Power source	Seed metering device	Hopper/drum capacity (kg)	Row spacing (cm)	Type of furrow opener	Furrow openers (no.)
Implement factory seed drill (3-row)	45	Human	Plastic roller with small round depressions	2.5	15	Cultivator type	3
Implement factory seed-cum-fertilizer drill (2-row)	30	Human	Plastic roller with small round depressions	2.0	15	Cultivator type	2
Annapurna seed drill (5-row)	75	Human	Drum with holes on the periphery. Circular iron belt regulates the size of openings.	4.5	15	Hoe type	5
Annapurna seed-cum-fertilizer drill (3-row)	35	Human	Drum with holes on the periphery. Circular iron belt regulates the size of openings.	2.5	15	Hoe type	3
CAET seed drill (3-row)	52	Bullock	Wooden roller with small round depressions mounted on the shaft	6	20	Cultivator type	3
CAET seed drill (5-row)	70	Bullock	Wooden roller with small round depressions mounted on the shaft	10	15	Cultivator type	5

Table 2. Efficiency of seed drills. Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, 1983-86.

Drill	Seed placement depth (cm)	SDE (%)	Plant population (no./row length)	EUE (kg grain/MJ)	CPI
Implement factory seed drill (3-row)	2.85	80	25	21.83	2.70
Implement factory seed-cum-fertilizer drill (2-row)	2.87	81	28	23.03	3.33
Annapurna seed drill (5-row)	1.43	65	20	19.13	1.40
Annapurna seed drill (2-row)	2.85	67	23	12.22	1.46
CAET seed drill (3-row)	3.20	77	24	4.78	1.34
CAET seed drill (5-row)	1.70	78	26	8.19	1.76
Broadcast	0.86	62	120 (per m ²)	3.22	0.62

after sowing (DAS) and 25% N at 40 DAS.

Data on average depth of seed placement, seed distribution efficiency (SDE), plant population/ m-row length,

energy use efficiency (EUE), and comparative performance index (CPI = product of energy, SDE, and grain yield factors) are in Table 2. The two-row implement factory seed-cum-fertilizer

drill had the highest CPI (3.33), SDE (81%), and number of plants/m-row (28). The three-row drill appeared to have had higher friction in the metering device. □

Environmental analysis

Effect of season on rice response, production efficiency, and recovery of applied N

M. A. Salam, Cropping Systems Research Centre, Karamana 695002, Trivandrum; and S. Subramanian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We studied the response, production efficiency, and recovery of applied N in rice, with and without soil-applied granular insecticides during the southwest monsoon (Jun-Sep 1982), northeast monsoon (Sep-Dec 1982), summer (Jan-Apr 1983), and southwest monsoon (Jan-Sep 1983).

Soil was clay loam, pH 8.2, with 1% organic matter, 196-9.5-200 ppm available NPK, 598 ppm total soil N, and 0.4 ppm DTPH extractable Zn. The experiments were factorial combinations

of 4 levels of N (0, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha) and 3 levels of insecticides (no insecticide, carbofuran 3% granular at 0.75 kg ai/ha, and phorate 10% granules at 1.0 kg ai/ha) in a randomized block design with 6 replications.

Rice response to N (kg grain produced: kg of N applied) and N recovery were highest when N was applied with carbofuran or phorate (see table).

Across the seasons, response and N recovery were higher in summer; production efficiency was higher in the northeast monsoon season. □

Response, production efficiency, and recovery of N applied with and without insecticide, by season.^a Coimbatore, India, 1982-83.

	SWM 1982	NEM 1982	SUM 1983	SWM 1983
<i>Response (kg grain:kg N)</i>				
N alone	12	12	16	21
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	19	20	25	22
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	20	21	26	25
<i>Production efficiency (kg grain:kg N)</i>				
N alone	39	70	45	56
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	34	12	41	56
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	38	23	44	66
<i>N recovery (%)</i>				
N alone	28	17	38	34
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	55	29	62	39
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	53	29	58	34

^aSWM = southwest monsoon, NEM = northeast monsoon, SUM = summer.

Farming systems

Growth and yield of wet season rice with tilapia fish

S. K. Datta and S. H. Ghosh, Field Crop Research Station, Bardhaman; and C. N. Bairagya, Radha Fish Farm, Bardhaman, West Bengal, India

We studied growth and yield of rice and fish in the Cropping Systems Research site at Memari in 1987 (Jun-Dec) wet season. The experiment consisted of a plot of rice without fish and one of rice with tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*).

Soil was clay loam with pH 6.5 - 7.0.

Plots were thoroughly plowed and 9 t farmyard manure/ ha incorporated. Plots were 20 × 38 m with a shallow 75- × 50-cm perimeter canal and a trapezoidal protective dike bounding the canal. To encourage better fish movement, 2 central drains, each 50 cm wide and 30 cm deep, were dug lengthwise across the plot of rice with fish.

Pankaj, a recommended photoperiod-sensitive lowland rice variety, was transplanted, 2 seedlings at 15- × 20-cm spacing/hill, in early Aug, with 100 kg N/ha applied 1/2 at land preparation and 1/2 in equal splits 1 mo after transplanting and 1 wk before flowering; 18 kg P and 33 kg K/ha were added at land preparation. Pump water was used

Growth and yield of rice + fish at Bardhaman, West Bengal, 1987 wet season.

Characteristic	Rice without fish	Rice + fish
<i>Rice</i>		
Plant height (cm)	133.2	120.8
Effective tillers/plant	12.0	15.2
Panicle length (cm)	26.4	26.8
Grains/panicle	158.2	178.4
Grain yield (t/ha)	4.1	4.9
Straw yield (t/ha)	5.2	6.0
<i>Fish</i>		
Recovery (%)	—	81.3
Increase in length (cm)	—	8.2
Increase in weight (g)	—	96.4
Fish yield (t/ha)	—	0.7

to irrigate as needed. Water depth, 3-5 cm at the outset, was gradually increased to 10-12 cm.